

FINAL PROGRAMME

3rd

Annual Congress of the
European Society for
Paediatric Anaesthesiology

ESPA 2011

PALMA DE MALLORCA

22-24 September

www.espa2011.es

Organized by

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EUROPEAN SOCIETY
FOR PAEDIATRIC ANAESTHESIOLOGY

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ABSTRACTS OF POSTER PRESENTATIONS

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for Paediatric Anaesthesiology
Palma de Mallorca, September 22nd – 24th 2011

0050 **Cortisol, Leptin and a Blood Sugar as a Good Stress Indicator During General Anaesthesia with Different Opioid Analgetics in Children**

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Introduction: A stressful response to an operation is followed by increased secretion of the hypophysis hormone and by activating the sympathetic nervous system. Cortisol is considered to be the most significant mediator to stress reaction. Cortisol has complex effects on the metabolism of carbo-hydrates, fats and proteins. Leptin is a hormone discovered in 1994. The balance of leptine and hypothalamo-hypophysis-adrenaline axis has a clinical significance. In the early stage of stress the level of leptine decreases with the subsequent increase of the cortisol level.

The level of glucoses becomes directly proportional to the level of catecholamine in the blood, and it is also proportional to the intensity of the surgical intervention. Opioid analgetics during the anaesthesia have the leading role in the modulation and suppression of the stress response to a surgical trauma.

Aim: The aim of the study was to determine which of the applied opioid analgetics brings the most powerful blockade of the stress response with the smallest side-effects in children.

Methods: Clinically prospective study included 150 boys, aged 2-5 years, belonged to the ASA I and II group, who had herniectomy or orchidopexy, as a part of a day surgery. The introduction into anesthesia was equal – propofol (2,5 mg/kg), rocuronium (0,6 mg/kg) and bolus dose of opioid analgesics. Maintenance of anaesthesia was – continuous propofol infusion, rocuronium application as a relaxant; the respiratory way was maintained by laryngeal mask and the ventilation was controlled or assisted by the mixture of oxygen/air (50%:50%). The examinees were divided into three groups of fifty depending on the applied opioid analgesics (fentanyl, alfentanil, remifentanil).

Results: The fentanyl group has the highest glucosis values in the blood. The examinees of fentanyl group had the highest increase in the cortisol level in the blood at the moment of incision and awakening time. The lowest increase in cortisol was recorded in the remifentanil group. A significant decrease in leptin was registered at the moment of awakening in the fentanyl group and in the remifentanil group at the moment of incision.

Conclusion: From the results we may conclude that the remifentanil is the opioid analgetic with the highest suppressing effect on the stress response to surgical intervention in children.

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